

SEAMARK DELIVERABLE 10.1: COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION & EXPLOITATION PLAN

Frederick Bruce¹, Efthalia Arvaniti¹, Urd Grandorf Bak², Katrin Gregersen², Ólavur Gregersen², Céline Boechat³, Petter Olsen³, Morten Heide³, Ove Johansen³, Unn Laksá⁴

Public summary of
confidential report

¹SUBMARINER Network for Blue Growth EEIG, Berlin, Germany, ²Ocean Rainforest Ap/S, Tórshavn, Faroe Islands, ³NOFIMA, Tromsø, Norway, ⁴Sjókovin - Blue Resource, Leirvik, Faroe Islands.

Edited by:

Frederick Bruce & Maya Miltell,
SUBMARINER NETWORK for Blue
Growth EEIG, Berlin, Germany

Primary contact for further information: Maya Miltell, mimi@submariner-network.eu

Reviewed by:

Urd Grandorf Bak, Ocean Rainforest
Ap/S Faroe Islands; Céline Boechat,
NOFIMA, Tromsø, Norway; Efthalia
Arvaniti, Angela Schulz-Zehden &
Maya Miltell, SUBMARINER NETWORK
for Blue Growth EEIG, Berlin,
Germany

Summary:

Beneficiaries of Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 funding must carry out activities to increase the impact of their project results. They must share research results with the scientific community, commercial players, civil society and policymakers and take action to use their project results for commercial purposes, to tackle societal problems or in policymaking. Communication is defined as promotion of actions and results to multiple stakeholders through a well-designed strategy, clear messaging and selection of the right media channels.

Due Date: 30.09.2022

Submission Date: 20.09.2022

Accepted Date: 30.09.2022

Updated date: 12.04.2024

Deliverable Reference: D10.1

Work Package / Task:

10 / T10.4 Communication,
Dissemination and Exploitation Plan
(CDEP)

Keywords:

algae, macroalgae, seaweed,
biorefinery, commercialisation, blue
bioeconomy, phycology, food tech,
communication, dissemination,
exploitation

The objective in communication is to engage stakeholders, attract expert interest in the project, generate market demand and raise awareness of publicly funded projects to showcase success stories from European collaboration efforts.

Dissemination is defined as the process through which results are made publicly available. This includes publishing in scientific magazines, presenting at targeted conferences and events, and developing databases for further use. The objective is to maximise the project's impact; to make resources available for further research; to advance the state-of-the-art and make scientific research available for the common good.

Exploitation is defined as the concrete use of results, whether commercially, socially or politically. This is achieved by creating roadmaps, prototypes and software to share skills, knowledge and data. The objective is to provide policy recommendations and benefit the economy by tackling specific problems or meeting existing demands.

The SeaMark project is an Innovation Action, defined as an Action primarily consisting of activities directly aiming at producing plans and arrangements or designs for new, altered or improved products, processes or services. The SeaMark consortium deliberately includes a strong industry representation to facilitate these innovations. This of course means that the risk of disputes related to Intellectual Property (IP) is increased. The SeaMark Consortium Agreement clearly lays out the terms of reference through which partners can avoid or resolve such disputes. The Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Plan (CDEP) focuses on the amplification of all project

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101060379. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor REA can be held responsible for them.

activities not subject to intellectual property in order to preserve the economic competitiveness of the industry partners. It provides methodologies and a roadmap to maximise the project's outcomes and long-term impacts, be it through stakeholder mapping, segmentation, innovative communication channels or organisation of targeted events. KPIs for impact analysis, CDE aims, key messages, CDE channels and activities are defined.